

**Ancient relicts or recent immigrants? Different dating strategies
alter diversification scenarios of New Zealand aquatic beetles
(Coleoptera: Hydrophilidae: *Berosus*)**

Matthias Seidel, Vít Sýkora, Richard A. B. Leschen, Bruno Clarkson
and Martin Fikáček

Supplementary material S2

Results of phylogenetic analyses

Topology analysis: maximum likelihood analysis

Berosus dataset

0.04

Topology analysis: Bayesian inference

Berosus dataset

Topology analysis: maximum likelihood analysis

Hydrophilidae dataset

0.06

Topology analysis: Bayesian inference

Hydrophilidae dataset

Dating analysis #1:

Berosus dataset (species only) - dated by *cox1* rate from Papadopoulou et al. (2010)

node labels: node age

bars: 95% credibility intervals of node age

blue branches: *Berosus*

red branches: New Zealand *Berosus*

Dating analysis #2:

Berosus dataset (species only) - dated by *cox1*+16S rates
from Papadopoulou et al. (2010)

node labels: node age

bars: 95% credibility intervals of node age

blue branches: *Berosus*

red branches: New Zealand *Berosus*

Dating analysis #3:

Berosus dataset (species only) - dated by *cox1*+16S+28S rates from Papadopoulou et al. (2010)

node labels: node age

bars: 95% credibility intervals of node age

blue branches: *Berosus*

red branches: New Zealand *Berosus*

Dating analysis #4:

Hydrophilidae dataset - lognormal priors, codons not subdivided

branch labels: posterior probability

node labels: node age

bars: 95% credibility intervals of node age

blue branches: *Berosus*

red branches: New Zealand *Berosus*

Dating analysis #5:

Hydrophilidae dataset - uniform priors, codons not subdivided

branch labels: posterior probability

node labels: node age

bars: 95% credibility intervals of node age

blue branches: *Berosus*

red branches: New Zealand *Berosus*

Dating analysis #7:

Hydrophilidae dataset - uniform priors, codons subdivided

branch labels: posterior probability

node labels: node age

bars: 95% credibility intervals of node age

blue branches: *Berosus*

red branches: New Zealand *Berosus*

Dating analysis #8:

Berosus dataset (species only) - stem Berosus constraint from Toussaint & Short (2018) implemented as truncated normal prior

node labels: node age

bars: 95% credibility intervals of node age

blue branches: *Berosus*

red branches: New Zealand *Berosus*

Dating analysis #9:

Berosus dataset (species only) - stem Berosus constraint from Toussaint & Short (2018) implemented as fixed prior

node labels: node age

bars: 95% credibility intervals of node age

blue branches: *Berosus*

red branches: New Zealand *Berosus*

Dating analysis #10:

Berosus dataset (species only) - node constraints from Hydrophilidae analysis #4 (fixed stem *Berosus* and truncated normal 5 node constraints)

node labels: node age

bars: 95% credibility intervals of node age

blue branches: *Berosus*

red branches: New Zealand *Berosus*

Dating analysis #11 - preferred tree:

Berosus dataset (all specimens) - node constraints from Hydrophilidae analysis #4 (fixed stem *Berosus* and truncated normal 5 node constraints)

Dating analysis #12:

Berosus pallidipennis specimens, cox1+16S data only - coalescence analysis, constant population size, dated by cox1 rate from analysis #10/

Dating analysis #13:

Berosus pallidipennis specimens, cox1+16S data only - coalescence analysis, exponential population size, dated by cox1 rate from analysis #10/

BioGeoBEARS analyses

Ancestral reconstructions using models without J parameter

BioGeoBEARS analyses

Ancestral reconstructions using models with +J parameter

Comparison of likelihood and AIC of all models tested

	LnL	numparams	d	e	j	AICc	AICc_wt_vBest	likeli	AICc
DEC	-5.302153854	2	0.006435464	1.00E-12	0	18.60430771	0.397258711	0.397258711	18.60430771
DEC+J	-3.102154032	3	1.00E-12	1.00E-12	0.304665389	24.20430806	0.024157323	0.024157323	24.20430806
DIVALIKE	-5.038574881	2	0.020789201	1.00E-12	0	18.07714976	0.517064025	0.517064025	18.07714976
DIVALIKE+J	-2.802409025	3	1.00E-12	1.00E-12	0.265461667	23.60481805	0.032600661	0.032600661	23.60481805
BAYAREALIKE	-8.833440951	2	0.030186187	0.052812958	0	25.6668819	0.011626659	0.011626659	25.6668819
BAYAREALIKE+J	-3.436461671	3	1.00E-07	1.00E-07	0.283565281	24.87292334	0.017292622	0.017292622	24.87292334

Model tests for the complete Berosus dataset

Clock tests

(stepping stone in MrBayes: #ss ngen=255000 diagnfreq=2500)

	non-clock	strict-clock	relaxed:uniform	relaxed:birth-death
Run1	-13577.33	-13596.84	-13571.29	-13489.41
Run2	-13598.41	-13566.39	-13636.06	-13455.51
Mean	-13578.02	-13567.08	-13571.98	-13456.2

Topology tests

testing alternative placements of *B. halasi* - as sister to *B. maru*, or as sister to all other NZ species
(stepping stone in MrBayes: #ss ngen=255000 diagnfreq=2500)

	halasi+maru	halasi out
Run 1	-14905.50	-14916.39
Run 2	-14909.64	-14913.68
Mean	-14906.18	-14914.31

Comparison of coalescence models

testing constant population size versus exponential population size

Tracer, AICM approach

Trace	AICM	S.E.	constant popsize	exponential popsize
constant popsize	8276.897	+/- 0.132	-	4.00
exponential popsize	8280.898	+/- 0.195	-4.00	-